

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some 2- and 8-Substituted Dibenzothiophene Propanoylamino Acid Derivatives

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The synthesis of different 3-(2-caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-VIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXIII) and 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XXXI-XXXV), corresponding hydrazides and some dipeptide methyl ester derivatives (IV-XLIII) have been achieved employing the carbodiimide and azide methods. Amongst the compounds synthesized, nine of various 2- and 8-substituted dibenzothiophene propanoylamino acid derivatives (IV, VII, X, XX, XXIII, XXVII, XXXI, XXXII and XXXV) were found to possess antimicrobial activities towards different microorganisms.

SEVERAL dibenzothiophene derivatives have been synthesized and found to possess antibacterial and antifungal activities^{1,2}, and to act as carcinogenic agents³. Recently, we reported the synthesis of some benzothiazoles, aminothiazoles and thiophene as well as other heterocyclic compounds incorporating amino acid and peptide moieties⁴⁻⁸. Some of these compounds displayed antimicrobial properties⁴⁻⁸.

In continuation of our previous studies, we have synthesized a new class of 3-(2-caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-VIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XXXI-XXXV) and some of their corresponding hydrazides (IX-XIII, XXIV-XXVIII and XXXVI-XXXIX) and dipeptide methyl esters derivatives (XIV-XVIII, XXIX-XXX and XL-XLIII). These compounds have also been tested for biological activity.

3-(2-Caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-VIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXIII) and 3-(8-nitro-2-caronyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XXXI-XXXV) were prepared by the carbodiimide method. Coupling of the propionic acid derivatives (I-III) with amino acid methyl ester hydrochlorides in THF containing triethylamine and using the dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) technique afforded the corresponding propanoylamino acid methyl ester derivatives (IV-VIII, XIX-XXIII and XXXI-XXXV). Complete acid hydrolysis of VI, XX and XXXII (6 N HCl; 24 hr) afforded valine.

Hydrazinolysis of the methyl esters (IV-VIII, XIX-XXIII and XXXI-XXXV) in ethanol gave the corresponding hydrazides (IX-XIII, XXIV-XXVIII and XXXVI-XXXIX) as crystalline solids which gave the positive benzidine and silver nitrate reactions.

Synthesis of the dipeptide methyl ester derivatives (XIV-XVIII, XXIX-XXX and XL-XLIII) was achieved starting from the hydrazides (IX-XIII, XXIV-XXVIII and XXXVI-XXXIX) which were converted into the corresponding azides. The azides on coupling with the free amino acid methyl esters furnished the dipeptides (XIV-XVIII, XXIX-XXX and XL-XLIII), which were isolated and purified in the usual manner⁹. The dipeptide methyl esters gave deep blue complexes with copper(II), λ_{\max} 630-650 nm.

Complete acid hydrolysis of XIV and XL (6 N HCl; 24 hr) afforded serine and leucine.

The ir spectra of compounds (IV-XVIII) showed characteristic bands at 3320, 3080 (NH, CONH); 1780, 1720 (>C=O); 2960, 2870 ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$); 1650, 1550, 1360 (amide I, II and III), 2920, 1450, 1290, 1080 (dibenzothiophene residue) and other bands characteristic of the amino acid or dipeptide and dibenzothiophene residues. The uv spectra of compounds (IV-XVIII) showed λ_{\max} (log ϵ) at 328 (4.95) and 269 (4.56), characteristic of the dibenzothiophene chromophore. The nmr spectra of compounds (IV-XVIII) exhibited seven dibenzothiophene protons in the range δ 7.5-8.7, four propanoyl protons ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$) at δ 3.46-3.52, the NH amide proton at δ 5.56 and other protons assignable to aromatic and amino acid residues.

The ir spectra of compounds (XIX-XLIII) showed characteristic bands at 3360, 3080 (NH, CONH); 1760, 1720 (>C=O); 2960, 2840 ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$); 1650, 1550, 1320 (amide I, II and III); 1380, 1220, 1080 (S and SO_2); 1640, 1490, 1380 (NO_2) and other bands characteristic of the amino acid or dipeptide and dibenzothiophene residues. The uv spectra of compounds (XIX-XLIII) showed λ_{max} ($\log \epsilon$) at 328 (4.87) and 268 (4.53), characteristic of the dibenzothiophene chromophore. The nmr spectra of compounds (XIX-XLIII) exhibit six dibenzothiophene protons in the range δ 7.6-8.4, four propanoyl protons at δ 3.49, the NH amide proton at δ 5.64 and other protons assignable to aromatic and amino acid residues.

Compounds IV-XLIII were prepared and characterized for the first time. All the synthesized compounds (IV-XLIII) gave ir, uv and nmr spectra consistent with their assigned structures.

Compounds IV-XVIII, Type-(A)

Compounds Type (B) XIX-XXX, X=S
XXXI-XLIII, X=SO₂

Biological activity :

The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds were tested using the hole plate and filter paper disc methods¹⁰⁻¹². The results were compared with the activity of the parent dibenzothiophene-propanoic acid derivatives (I-III), 3-(2-Carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoyl-L-Ser-OMe (IV) and the corresponding L-Tyr-OMe (VII) and L-Val-N₂H₃ (X) derivatives were found to possess high antimicrobial activities against *B. subtilis* (ICC-strain), *B. cereus* (NRRL-B-569) and *B. mycoides* (USSR) with MIC ranging from 10-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ but they were inactive against *E. coli* (NRRL-B-210), *S. typhosa* (NRRL-B-573) and *P. chrysogenum* (MIC 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). 3-(8-Nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoyl-L-Val-OMe (XX) and the corresponding L-Tyr-OMe (XXIII) and L-Phe-OMe (XXVII) derivatives showed antimicrobial effects and gave promising results against *B. subtilis*, *B. cereus*, *B. mycoides* (MIC 25-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and *P. chrysogenum* (MIC 125-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). They were inactive against *E. coli* and *S. typhosa* (MIC 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). 3-(8-Nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoyl-L-Ser-OMe (XXXI) and the corresponding L-Val-OMe (XXXII) and L-Tyr-OMe (XXXV) derivatives had a marked growth inhibitory effect against *B. subtilis*, *B. cereus*, *B. mycoides* and *E. coli* (MIC 25-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The remaining amino acid and dipeptide

derivatives were inactive towards all the tested microorganisms.

The present investigation revealed that introduction of nitro substituent in the 8-position in the dibenzothiophene residue in combination with propanoyl and amino acid moieties gave dibenzothiophene-propanoylamino acid derivatives of highly specific biological properties. The L-Val, L-Ser, L-Tyr and L-Phe derivatives were found to possess high antimicrobial properties when compared with the corresponding L-Leu derivatives. Elongation of the peptide chain did not affect the biological activity of these compounds, since the synthesis of dibenzothiophene-propanoyldipeptide esters did not enhance or modify the biological properties of these derivatives. Other pharmacological studies are in progress.

Experimental

All melting points are corrected. Thin layer chromatography (R_f value) was made on Silica Gel-G (B.D.H.) using benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) as the solvent system and an iodine-potassium iodide (20%) or chlorosulphonic acid-acetic acid mixture (1:3) as the detection reagent. Benzidine, ninhydrin, silver nitrate and hydroxamate reactions were used for detection of the amino acid derivatives on paper chromatograms (spot reactions). The electrophoretic mobilities (E) were measured at 1000 V, 2 hr in pyridine-acetate buffer (pH 5.6). The uv spectra (λ_{max} in nm) in ethanol solution were recorded with a Unicam SP 8000; ir spectra (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) were measured with a Unicam SP 1200 in KBr pellets and nmr data were obtained on Varian EM-360 L spectrophotometer in DMSO-d₆ and shifts are reported in δ ppm relative to internal TMS. Optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ were taken in a Zeiss polarimeter with 1 dm tube, c=3 in ethanol.

3-(2-Carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoic acid (I), 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoic acid (II) and 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoic acid (III) were prepared according to reported procedures^{14,15}.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (IV-VIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XIX-XXIII) and 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoylamino acid methyl esters (XXXI-XXXV): To a solution of amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.011 mol) in THF (100 ml) was added triethylamine (6 ml). The solution was stirred for 20 min at 20° and cooled to 0°. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and washed with THF (5 ml). To the filtrate at 0° was added 3-(2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoic acid, 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoic acid or 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide)propanoic acid (I-III, 0.01 mol) in THF (120 ml) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (0.01 mol). The mixture was then stirred for 2 hr

at 0°, left for 24 hr at 0° and for another 24 hr at room temperature. The dicyclohexyl urea was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo*. The residual solid was recrystallized from ethanol, methanol, water or their mixtures. The products (IV-VIII, XIX-XXIII and XXXI-XXXV) were soluble in alcohols, DMF, dioxane, THF, DMSO and nitromethane and insoluble in water, ether and pet. ether. The materials were chromatographically

homogeneous (detection with iodine solution, benzidine or chlorosulphonic acid-acetic acid mixture) and showed negative ninhydrin reaction.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid hydrazides (IX-XIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene)propanoylamino acid hydrazides (XXIV-XXVIII) and 3-(8-nitro-2-carbonyldibenzothiophene-5,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF VARIOUS SUBSTITUTED DIBENZOTHIOPHENE PROPANOYL-AMINO ACID AND DIPEPTIDE DERIVATIVES(IV-XLIII)

Compd.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	R _f	[α] _D ²⁰ (c=3, ethanol)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
Compounds (IV-XVIII) of the type A								
IV	L-Ser-OMe	70	165-67	0.62	+209.5	62.44 (62.33)	4.98 (4.93)	3.73 (3.63)
V	L-Leu-OMe	86	175-77	0.58	+205	67.19 (67.15)	6.12 (6.08)	3.56 (3.40)
VI	L-Val-OMe	90	150-52	0.63	+153	66.53 (66.49)	5.81 (5.79)	3.62 (3.52)
VII	L-Tyr-OMe	81	200-2	0.66	+188.5	67.87 (67.67)	5.11 (4.98)	3.09 (3.03)
VIII	L-Phe-OMe	85	168-70	0.78	+225	70.21 (70.11)	5.23 (5.16)	3.21 (3.14)
IX	L-Ser-N ₂ H ₂	75	220-22	0.57	+243	59.41 (59.22)	5.07 (4.93)	10.93 (10.90)
X	L-Val-N ₂ H ₂	73	168-70	0.55	+105.8	63.52 (63.47)	5.87 (5.79)	10.61 (10.57)
XI	L-Leu-N ₂ H ₂	78	200-2	0.68	+188	64.41 (64.23)	6.21 (6.08)	10.31 (10.21)
XII	L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₂	75	228-30	0.72	+145.5	65.11 (65.07)	5.03 (4.98)	9.17 (9.11)
XIII	L-Phe-N ₂ H ₂	68	179-81	0.69	+134	67.99 (67.41)	5.21 (5.16)	9.55 (9.43)
XIV	L-Ser-L-Leu-OMe	60	220-22	0.72	+212	62.73 (62.65)	6.09 (6.02)	5.71 (5.62)
XV	L-Tyr-L-Leu-OMe	55	193-95	0.67	+88.5	66.93 (66.89)	5.98 (5.92)	4.85 (4.87)
XVI	L-Tyr-L-Phe-OMe	65	203-5	0.74	+136.5	69.13 (69.07)	5.32 (5.26)	4.66 (4.60)
XVII	L-Phe-L-Leu-OMe	61	210-12	0.78	+195	68.93 (68.81)	6.12 (6.09)	4.98 (5.01)
XVIII	L-Phe-L-Tyr-OMe	57	231-33	0.77	+232.5	69.11 (69.07)	5.47 (5.26)	4.71 (4.60)
Compounds (XIX-XXX) of the type B, X=S								
XIX	L-Ser-OMe	82	170-72	0.64	+261	55.93 (55.81)	4.22 (4.18)	6.77 (6.51)
XX	L-Val-OMe	79	180-82	0.69	+277	59.81 (59.72)	5.03 (4.97)	6.44 (6.33)
XXI	L-Leu-OMe	86	200-2	0.59	+253	60.63 (60.52)	5.48 (5.26)	6.31 (6.14)
XXII	L-Phe-OMe	83	177-79	0.58	+222.5	63.70 (63.67)	4.51 (4.48)	5.80 (5.71)
XXIII	L-Tyr-OMe	85	185-87	0.63	+291	61.71 (61.66)	4.40 (4.34)	5.56 (5.53)
XXIV	L-Ser-N ₂ H ₂	55	181-83	0.53	+115	53.22 (53.02)	4.20 (4.18)	13.13 (13.02)
XXV	L-Val-N ₂ H ₂	50	170-72	0.69	+127	57.09 (57.01)	5.03 (4.97)	12.67 (12.66)
XXVI	L-Leu-N ₂ H ₂	56	208-10	0.56	+99	57.93 (57.89)	5.30 (5.26)	12.31 (12.28)
XXVII	L-Phe-N ₂ H ₂	52	198-200	0.77	+113.5	61.28 (61.22)	4.53 (4.48)	11.40 (11.42)
XXVIII	L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₂	55	192-94	0.71	+150	59.42 (59.28)	4.66 (4.34)	11.31 (11.06)
XXIX	L-Leu-L-Phe-OMe	60	233-35	0.72	+35.5	63.81 (63.68)	5.55 (5.47)	7.03 (6.96)
XXX	L-Val-L-Leu-OMe	65	187-89	0.79	+75.3	60.66 (60.54)	5.97 (5.94)	7.66 (7.56)

(Table 1 Contd.)

Compounds (XXXI-XLIII) of the type B, X=SO ₂								
XXXI	L-Ser-OMe	85	240-42	0.75	+40.5	52.06 (51.94)	4.02 (3.89)	6.11 (6.06)
XXXII	L-Val-OMe	80	190-92	0.65	+76.5	56.01 (55.69)	4.93 (4.64)	6.02 (5.90)
XXXIII	L-Leu-OMe	87	198-200	0.69	+75.8	56.75 (56.55)	4.98 (4.91)	5.77 (5.73)
XXXIV	L-Phe-OMe	85	231-33	0.78	+39.6	59.81 (59.77)	4.22 (4.21)	5.40 (5.36)
XXXV	L-Tyr-OMe	84	206-8	0.68	+68	58.11 (57.99)	4.18 (4.08)	5.18 (5.20)
XXXVI	L-Ser-N ₂ H ₂	55	212-14	0.77	+171	49.37 (49.35)	3.91 (3.89)	12.13 (12.12)
XXXVII	L-Val-N ₂ H ₂	60	210-12	0.79	+154	53.23 (53.16)	4.71 (4.64)	11.93 (11.81)
XXXVIII	L-Leu-N ₂ H ₂	63	180-82	0.73	+114.5	54.11 (54.09)	5.04 (4.91)	11.62 (11.47)
XXXIX	L-Tyr-N ₂ H ₂	58	201-3	0.69	+151	55.81 (55.76)	4.22 (4.08)	10.44 (10.40)
XL	L-Ser-L-Leu-OMe	55	163-65	0.62	+136	54.33 (54.26)	5.09 (5.04)	7.37 (7.30)
XLI	L-Ser-L-Phe-OMe	65	179-81	0.70	+189	57.19 (57.14)	4.50 (4.43)	6.85 (6.89)
XLII	L-Tyr-L-Ser-OMe	53	169-71	0.59	+171.5	55.77 (55.68)	4.37 (4.32)	6.81 (6.72)
XLIII	L-Tyr-L-Phe-OMe	65	187-89	0.57	+228.5	61.62 (61.31)	4.75 (4.52)	6.15 (6.13)

* Electrophoretic mobilities (E) for all the compounds synthesized (IV-XLIII)=zero.

5-dioxide)propanoylamino acid hydrazides (XXXVI-XXXIX): Each of the methyl ester derivatives (IV-VIII, XIX-XXIII, or XXXI-XXXV) (0.01 mol) was dissolved in abs. ethanol (80 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (85%, 2.5 ml; 0.05 mol) added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hr and left 24 hr at 20°. The crystalline products (IX-XIII, XXIV-XXVIII and XXXVII-XXXIX) were filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from methanol. All the hydrazides were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with iodine solution or benzidine) and gave positive silver nitrate reaction.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(2-carboxyindolyl)propanoyldipeptide methyl esters (XIV-XVIII), 3-(8-nitro-2-carboxyindolyl)propanoyldipeptide methyl esters (XXIX-XXX) and 3-(8-nitro-2-carboxyindolyl-5,5-dioxide)propanoyldipeptide methyl esters (XL-XLIII): The amino acid hydrazide (IX-XIII, XXIV-XXVII and XXXVI-XXXIX) (0.002 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (6 ml), 5 N HCl (3 ml) and water (35 ml) and cooled to -5°. Sodium nitrite (0.53 g) in water (4 ml) was added and the mixture stirred for 5 min at 0°. The azide was extracted with ethyl acetate (70 ml) and the extract washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate (3%), water and dried (Na₂SO₄).

Compounds (XIV-XVIII, XXIX-XXX and XL-XLIII) were prepared by the addition of ethyl acetate solution of the corresponding azide to a cooled (-5°) solution of the free amino acid methyl ester (prepared from 0.0025 mol of the amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride and 0.9 ml triethylamine as described earlier⁹), and stirring of the reaction

mixture for 6 hr at 4° and keeping it for 24 hr at 0° and for another 24 hr at room temperature. It was washed successively with HCl (0.5 N), water, sodium bicarbonate (3%) and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residual material was recrystallized from ethanol or methanol. All dipeptides were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with iodine solution and benzidine) and showed negative ninhydrin and silver nitrate reactions.

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